

**TURKISH AND ETHIOPIAN TEACHERS' VIEWS
ABOUT STUDENTS' UNDESIRABLE BEHAVIOURS IN
THE CLASSROOM AND THE TECHNIQUES THEY USE TO
COPE UP WITH: A CASE STUDYⁱ**

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Abstract:

The overall purpose of this study was to identify teachers' views about types and causes of students' undesirable behaviours and the techniques they use to cope up with. This study is qualitative in nature, and in the pattern of a holistic multiple case study. To identify the schools, the researchers used convenience sampling technique. The work group was determined using maximum variable sampling. As a result, the working group consisted of four participants from Turkish school and four from Ethiopian school. The data were collected by a semi-structured questionnaire interviewing the participants face to face. The data were analysed by the help of computer program called Nvivo using content analysis technique. The observed behaviours common to both schools were being late, cheating, not doing the given tasks, talking without permission during the lesson, hyperactivity and lack of attention, complaining about their teacher to family, not paying attention to personal hygiene and being rude. On the other hand, In Ethiopia, attaching nickname to friends, picking up and leaving the class in the middle of lesson, eating and drinking at the wrong time, insulting and not sitting properly; in Turkey producing a variety of excuses and complaints, silence, selfishness, naughtiness, swearing, lack of interest in cultural activities and theatre play, smoking

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cigarettes secretly were undesirable behaviours determined peculiar to each culture. A close, positive and supportive relationship between all school stakeholders is essential for developing a mutual relationship of respect and for managing undesirable behaviours successfully.

Keywords: undesirable behaviours, classroom management, students' behaviours

1. Introduction

Students' undesirable behaviours in school are not new phenomena. Discipline is among the basic ingredient that plays a crucial role in school system (Amogne, 2014, p.23). Predominantly, discipline problems occur when a student refuses to obey rules of the classroom or school. Lack of discipline in school makes it difficult to teach effectively. Maintaining class order and peace is a primary concern of teachers (Doyle, 1984). One of the effects of student indiscipline on teaching learning process is poor performance. Since much time is spent on discipline cases, less time on teaching, and this means that the contents are not completed hence students' inadequate preparation for the examinations and learning (Alemayehu, 2012, p.16). Maintaining class order is a primary concern of teachers (Doyle, 1984).

Misbehaviour in schools and in the classroom is considered to be a serious problem to all those interested in the problematic of teaching (Oliveira, & Amândio, 2013, p.9). Kyriacou (1997, p.121) defines undesirable behaviour as any behaviour from non-compliance such as not paying attention to overt undesirable behaviour such as throwing a missile across the room. Nearly in the same way, Feldhusen (1995) also defined it as "*disobedience or a violation of school expectations interfering with the orderly conduct of teaching*". Shrigley (1999) presented a more comprehensive definition that any behaviour that interrupts the teaching acts, or is psychologically or physically unsafe constitutes an undesirable behaviour. This definition comprises of behaviours that would not necessarily slow down the teaching act but is definitely psychologically or physically unsafe and needs teacher's attention.

The types of undesirable behaviours of students vary across teachers (Çetin, 2015, Alemayehu, 2012, p.43-44, & Getiye, 2015, p.39). They are also different across countries and level of class. For example, a study conducted in Singapore showed types of undesirable behaviours of students include: telling lies, being late for class; undesirable behaviour in class, vandalism, using abusive language, truancy, theft, and bullying, not doing homework, and defiance towards teachers, not bringing books to school, inappropriate appearance, negative attitude towards study and shop lifting (Tan &

Yuanshan, 1999, p.3). In Ethiopia, the most commonly observed students' undesirable behaviours in secondary schools of students in Guji Zone were ranked as follow: cheating on tests and in-class assignments, being late, failing to submit homework on time, leaving the school without permission, using mobile for illegal purpose at school, failing to bring necessary materials to class, being off task and carelessness, absenteeism, violating the school dress code (Getiye, 2015, p.39). But, according to Alemayehu (2012, p.43-44) study on Shamashemene secondary school students in Ethiopia, the top ranked frequently observed undesirable behaviours included: tardiness, absenteeism (truancy), and disturbing in the classroom like talking without permission, using cell phone etc., cheating on exams, copying assignment, and least efforts, fighting, extortion, coercion, mob action, as well as failing to follow teacher's instruction. There are evidences that some students also use her/his though outside the school. However, that undesirable that are life threatening as well as damaging the school property were found to be less prevalent. The findings of Amogne (2014, p.23) revealed that disciplinary problems in Ethiopia have been getting worse from time to time and ranges from frequent absenteeism to drinking alcohol and smoking cigarette. The Author added day dreaming, quarrelling, cheating, missing classes, inattentiveness and distributive behaviour are among the manifestations of the problem. Moreover, the undesired behaviours of students that Turkish classroom teachers faced in the classroom have been determined as not obeying the class rules, swearing, talking without permission, shyness, hyperactivity and lack of attention, and problems caused by watching violent TV programs (such as threatening) (Çetin, 2015). As can be seen from the findings of Balay and Sağlam, (2008) the most frequently observed undesirable behaviours also include: speaking without lift their hand, abusive speech, respond to questions by all at the same time, blame each other and coming to school without preparation. Lewis (1991) has distinguished three overlapping types of undesirable, namely: undesirable that inhibits the learner's own learning, undesirable by one learner, which is destructive to the learning of another, and undesirable which is disrespectful, defiant or abusive to the educator.

Because different kinds of undesirable behaviour and each one has, different causes which has negative impact on classroom management (Dhaliwal, 2013, p.3). To understand undesirables and teachers reactions to it, one must examine teacher attributions, or beliefs about the causes of behaviour. Teachers tend to attribute the cause for misbehaviour of the students in the school more, to external factors than to internal ones. A teacher who believes that a student's undesirable is caused by problems at home may feel no "ownership" of the problem and therefore be less likely to explore teacher-focused intervention strategies, like the use of different teaching

styles or a critical examination of their class environment (Oliveira & Amândio, 2013, p.9). According to the study of Tan, E. & Yuansha, C. (1999, p.8), teachers identify possible causes for the behavioural problems encountered to unconducive home environment, negative peer pressure, and poor parenting. Lack of parental guidance/supervision is the most frequently cited reason. The next to be blamed are adverse influences of the media promoting materialistic values.

Furthermore, student undesirable is deep-rooted in a complex web of factors internal and external to the schools. The principal causative factors are those related to parents, student, school and teacher; in order of importance. Top among the most important causes also include student related causes such as lack of interest and negative attitude as well as their inability to perform well/satisfactorily. Then follow, school and teacher related factors including the imbalance between the number of students and the school capacity, teacher's failure to integrate methods and contents with abilities and needs of learners, and lack of administrative support/lack of follow-up towards ensuring student disciplining. Other external factors included poor support by the government and community. Finally, the following teacher-related causes of student undesirable were identified: failure to integrate methods and contents with abilities and needs of learners, inability to maintain discipline, failure of teachers to adhere to existing disciplines, policies and orders (Getiye, 2015, p.45).

When teachers faced undesirable behaviours, they used different strategies. For example, Getiye, (2015, p.47) results were ranked below accordingly the mean values and the interview result of the respondents such as use collaborative strategies to resolve disciplinary issues, empower others to help make decisions pertaining to discipline, problem solving, and leadership, strengthening school and community relationship. Furthermore, principals have a safety and welfare segment staff meeting where relevant issues can be discussed and decided, use of tolerance developing smooth relationship, praising or awarding students for good.

In Turkey, research on classroom management and student misbehaviour in particular, has focused on several dimensions: the role of teacher in finding solutions for behavioural problems (Demirden, 1994), effects of physical setting, student-teacher interaction of classroom life in Maths, Science, Turkish and English classes (Başar,1994), and most commonly encountered misbehaviours and identification of supportive help leading teachers to prevent those misbehaviours (Özen and Batu, 1999) are some examples of studies that focused on classroom management issue. In another study, Atıcı (1999) attempted to identify the methods used by 73 Turkish and 51 English primary school teachers in dealing with student misbehaviour. It was found out that while English teachers dealt with misbehaviours more systematically and consistently,

Turkish teachers tended to deal with misbehaviours through experience. In Turkey as Çetin (2015) presented teachers' solutions to undesirable behaviours were punishments and awards, warning, ignoring, behaving more sincerely towards students, including students by means of activities, guidance service, giving assignment, making students sit in front of the class, and playing games. In other study, teachers exhibited mostly calling the student with their names as a kind of reaction against the undesirable that disrupt the flow of a lesson, preferring a reaction of gazing at student from the reactions that take the least learning time (Yilmaz, 2008). According to the study of Başar (2001) at primary schools, student may show undesirable behaviour because he/she does not know how to act. Sometimes a child knows behaviour, but he can act wrong because he does not know when to do it. Finally, the child knows what to do and when to do it, but he may show negative behaviour because he or she has forgotten the interlude. In most of these cases, the student may have to repeat the wrong behaviour.

This is universally acknowledging fact that good classroom management for solving undesirable behaviours of students in the classroom depends on the competencies of a teacher. Therefore, teachers should be more competent and well trained regarding on how to manage the classroom. Teachers should have a sound knowledge of teaching methodologies and classroom management. Effective classroom management is playing a crucial role in making teaching learning process more effective, productive and successful. Without effective classroom management, teaching learning process has no fruitful results and students cannot become successful in their academic achievement. According to Borg and Falzon (1990), variables such as teacher training and the extent of teaching experience are important moderator variables on teachers' perceptions of undesirable behaviour, although little research has examined relationships between these variables. A study by Alemayehu (2012) disclosed that students' disciplinary problem in Shashemene secondary school (Ethiopia) became serious and stressful through time. Then after the authors were thinking over it and many questions came in our mind. In addition, the researchers want to know the difference on the issues from teachers' perspectives. For filling this gap with some extent, the researchers were explored experienced Ethiopian and Turkish teachers' views about types and causes of students' undesirable behaviours and the techniques they use to cope up.

The overall aim of this study was to identify Ethiopian and Turkish teachers' views about types and causes of students' undesirable behaviours and the techniques they use to cope up with. To achieve this objective, the researcher raised the following questions.

1. What are the different types of students' undesirable behaviour as perceived by the teachers of primary schools?
2. What are the causes of undesirable behaviours in the classroom perceived by the teachers of primary schools?
3. What are the techniques used by teachers in managing the undesirable behaviours of the primary school students?
4. What are teachers' suggestions for other teachers regarding ways of managing the undesirable behaviours of the primary school students in the classroom?

As a whole, this research was believed to have different significance for students, ministry of education, teachers, schools, researchers and concerned citizens by increasing knowledge and information of what types and causes of students' undesirable behaviours and techniques that important to handle students' misbehaviour. It is also anticipated that based on the findings, those school administrators interested in managing the undesirable behaviours of students will explore the different classroom management approaches to encourage the development of informal social interactions and networks on the school among teachers and students. Finally, the study was recommending possible solutions, for the betterment of future of classroom management for teachers based on the suggestions of the participants. It may also serve as a springboard for other researchers to take in-depth study for further investigation in the field and issue.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study is qualitative in nature and employs the qualitative research design and specifically a holistic multiple case study because qualitative research is more concern with understanding individuals' perceptions of the world and seeking insights rather than statistical analysis (Silverman, 2005). In qualitative research design, the case study method allows investigators to retain the holistic and meaningful characteristics of real-life events (Yin, 2012). Case studies can establish cause and effect, indeed one of their strengths is that they observe effects in real contexts, recognizing that context is a powerful determinant of both causes and effects. Further, contexts are unique and dynamic; therefore, case studies investigate and report the complex dynamic and unfolding interactions of events, human relations and other factors in a unique instance (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007).

2.2 Working Group

The study was carried out in two schools. One in Antalya in Turkey and one in Ethiopia in Addis Ababa. In order to identify these schools, the researchers used convenience sampling technique. Data was collected through interview with maximum diversity sampling from a total eight, four from Turkey and four from Ethiopia. Two of senior teachers, one of assistance principal and the principal from each school have been selected. The choice to select assistance principals, principals and senior teachers were made by considering the topic of the research and to maximize the varieties of views from different school positions. The school management (assistant principals and principals) can be seen as the initiator of behaviour management policies in their school and senior teachers can be seen as the receiver and the one who implements and follows these policies regarding behaviour management in their school. Therefore, gathering data from a variety of interviewees depending on the role they play in their school could provide a relatively balanced set of viewpoints and variety of perceptions to analyse.

2.3 Data Gathering Instruments and Ethical Considerations

In this study, the school viewed as an instrumental case study, because investigations on students' undesirable behaviours were carried out in school setting. In order to investigate teachers' views on the types and causes of undesirable behaviours of the students and the techniques they used within the classroom, semi-structured interview was used. Because semi-structured interviews would provide an in depth exploration of the topic, allowed the researchers to change the order of questions, simplify the questions and to probe the interviews (Cohen et al., 2007). In addition, it also used to record the teachers' experiences, thoughts and feelings shared during the semi-structured interviews. Thus, the mapping of semi-interview questions were carried out in three major levels. Firstly, interviewers were asked an initial question as: How do they feel with the word undesirable behaviour of the students? What are their views on the types of undesirable behaviours in the classroom? What are their views about the causes of these each undesirable behaviours in classroom? What are the techniques that they used to cope up? At the end, from their experiences, their suggestions for other teachers regarding ways of managing the undesirable behaviours of the primary school students in the classroom.

Prior to data collection, the researchers sought approval to conduct research in the specified area and to explicitly sought the consent of participants who involved in this research and to ensured, as their responses will kept confidential, the purpose of the study was explained. The participants were informed that they could discontinue

participation at any time. Each participant was contacted and a convenient location and time was determined for the interview. Prior to the interview, the researchers asked the participants to sign a consent form and complete a demographic form of relevant background data.

2.4 Data Analysis Techniques

There is no one way to analyse and present qualitative interview data. The literature does suggest using three steps, which are labelled as organizing, summarizing and interpreting as a guide to data analysis (Ary et al., 2002). For organizing data, the researchers were look the notes that they have taken on the sheets of paper at the time of each interview and noting down the similarities, themes and interesting responses. If there is missing information, the researchers were listening to the digital recording of the complete interviews repeatedly as necessarily. After that, the researchers were made the interview data fully transcribed. The researchers sent a transcription of the interviews to each participant for checking and they invited to make any corrections. The step of summarizing by finding common themes, involved looking for repeating words and phrases and categorizing these into similar groups. The last stage is interpretation where the data were examined, analysed, contrasted and compared. In addition, data analysis process was aided by the use of a qualitative data analysis computer program called NVIVO, which used to facilitate and assist to analyse the data that have qualitative in nature. That is NVIVO does not perform the analysis but only supports the researcher doing the analysis by organizing data etc. (Cohen et al., 2007).

2.5 Validity and Reliability

In order to establish reliability and validity within this study, the following steps were implemented. The researchers initially “field test” all questionnaire with two teachers to assess the type of interview questions for use throughout the study and to ensure that the data from the questions are valid and reliable. Prior to interviewing, the processes of checking both sets of interview questions against the aim and key questions and the piloting of the questions were support the validity of this study. Reliability was assessed through test-retest reproducibility by asking some of the participants more than one occasion. Some of the questions were asked in more than one way to assess internal consistency. Acceptability was determined by asking the teachers how they found answering the questionnaire during the validity testing. This process was helping to identify main issues and form the basis of the type of interview questions to be used in the pilot study.

3. Findings

This chapter presented analysis of the data collected through interview from Ethiopian and Turkish teachers. All the eight participants were primary school teachers from two different primary schools in Ethiopia and Turkey. There were four from each school. This chapter organized in thematic approach and focused on socio-demographic characteristics of the sample, teachers' perceptions about the word undesirable behaviour of the students, teachers' view on the types of undesirable behaviours, their views about the causes of undesirable behaviour in classroom. Finally, the techniques teachers used when they faced undesirable behaviours and their suggestions for other teachers regarding ways of managing the undesirable behaviours of the primary school students in the classroom were presented. To do these, NVIVO were employed in the analyses of the variables under consideration. Teachers' responses throughout the presentation of the findings were identified as Et1-4, which representing teacher 1-principal, teacher 2-assistance principal, teacher 3 and 4-senior teachers etc. from Ethiopia. In additions, Tt1 to four were representing teacher 1-principal, teacher, 2-assistance principal teacher, 3 and 4-senior teachers etc. from Turkey respectively. It was organized into six aspects. These are:

A. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Participants	Gender	Position at school	Working years at present position	Total working years as a teacher	School
A	Male	Principal	4	21	GPS, Turkey
B	Male	Ass. principal	3	11	GPS, Turkey
C	Male	Teacher	24	24	GPS, Turkey
D	Male	Teacher	10	10	GPS, Turkey
E	Male	Principal	5	14	SKPS, Ethiopia
F	Female	Ass. principal	1	9	SKPS, Ethiopia
G	male	Teacher	9	11	SKPS, Ethiopia
H	Male	Teacher	10	11	SKPS, Ethiopia
A	Male	Principal	4	21	GPS, Turkey

As shown in table 1 above, the participants of this study were categorized by gender, position and working years at present position and totally as teacher. With regard to their gender, the majority 7(87.5%) of the respondents were male. In addition, all respondents had more than nine years of working experience as a teacher. They were senior teachers.

B. Teachers' perceptions about the word undesirable behaviour of the students.

Teachers were asked about what they feel with the word undesirable behaviour of the students and follow up questions related to this.

Ethiopian teachers defined undesirable behaviour of students as "...Any behaviour in the classroom that affects the learning environment negatively" (Et1), "...any behaviour that prevents educational efforts at school" (Et2), "behaviour that is not appropriate at the school but is done consciously" (Et3). Finally, Et4 defined as every behaviour that disturbs the course, makes it difficult to reach the target behaviours, or prevents it". Nearly in the same way, Turkish teachers also defined it as "When students do not keep up with the rules of students, that the so-called undesirable behaviour" (Tt1), "unwanted and unexpected behaviours of students in the classroom" (Tt3) and "any behaviour prevents the learner from learning, threatens the safety of other learner's friends, damage to school" (Tt4). In addition, Tt3 defined "If students do not behave in the way we expect, it is undesirable behaviour. According to the basic law our nation, it is generally expected that a student will be a good citizen, a good person, have a good profession by completing their education. Undesirable behaviours connected to this process the student not bringing back the behaviour we want".

C. Teachers' views on the types of undesirable behaviours in the classroom

The views of Ethiopian and Turkish teachers about the types of undesirable behaviours in the classroom were given in table 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2: Ethiopian Teachers' Views about the Types of Undesirable Behaviours in the Classroom

Themes	Sub-themes	Et1	Et2	Et3	Et4	n
Violations of School Regulations	Lateness	✓		✓	✓	3
	Picking up and leaving the class in the middle of lesson	✓				1
	Cheating	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
	Eating and drinking at the wrong Time		✓			1
	Not attending regularly in the class				✓	1
Doing something in private	Doing irrelevant activities in the class		✓		✓	2
Violations of school work requirement	Hyperactivity and lack of Concentration		✓			1
	Not doing home work	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Violations of seating arrangement	Not sitting properly		✓			1
Transgressions against	Disobedience to carry out		✓			1

Kelemu Zelalem Berhanu, Ali Sabanci
 TURKISH AND ETHIOPIAN TEACHERS' VIEWS ABOUT STUDENTS' UNDESIRABLE BEHAVIOURS IN
 THE CLASSROOM AND THE TECHNIQUES THEY USE TO COPE UP WITH: A CASE STUDY

teacher and school administrators	commands and instructions				
	Rudeness with teacher / talking back	✓	✓	✓	3
Violations of inter-personal relations (with other children)	Not having a health		✓		1
	Communication				
	Getting other children into trouble		✓	✓	2
	Insulting		✓		1
Undesirable personality traits and morality	attaching nickname		✓		1
	Being rude		✓		1
	Noisy speech		✓	✓	2
	Lying			✓	1
Damaging and stealing the property	Lack of personal hygiene		✓	✓	3
	Damaging school equipment		✓	✓	2
	Theft		✓		1

Table 2 summarizes the categorization of responses based on Ethiopian teachers' views on types of students' undesirable behaviours inside classroom. The responses were classified into eight main themes and six of them further were divided into 21 sub-themes. The common reported classroom undesirable behaviours were cheating and not doing the assigned tasks such as homework. Next, personal hygiene, being rude and late are the frequently reported behaviours' by three out of four (75%) teachers.

Participants' opinions on the subject were directly cited below:

“Students' being late, not doing assigned tasks , picking up and leaving in the middle of class, being rude, refusing to complete the assignments, cheating and taking the exam later stages of the conflict included more actions that bordered on violence” (Et1).

And,

“Mostly in the classroom are talking without permission during the lesson, hyperactivity and lack of attention, and behaving disrespectfully against teachers, make complain to teachers about friends , attach nickname to friends, disturb other friends in the lesson, to take someone else's belongings or materials without permission, not establish healthy communication with friends. The most common undesirable types of behaviour are presence in off-duty behaviour, eating and drinking illegally and acting at the wrong time, damage the equipment of school. In addition, disobedience to teacher, deceit and insult, talk too much, make noise with or without words, do not work, do not sitting properly, and do not pay attention to personal hygiene” (Et2).

“Do not pay attention to personal hygiene, do not do the given task such as homework, being late, lying, copy of his/ her homework from other students” (Et3).

At the last as mentioned by teacher Et4:

“Not attending in the class, being late, coming to school without preparation, talking to friends in classroom, harming oneself, friends and school property, dreaming for a long time or dealing with extracurricular activities in the class, not obeying the rules of cleanliness and etiquette, cheating on the exam, being rude to teachers and friends, abusive speech and disturbing friends are undesirable”.

Table 3: Turkish Teachers' Views about the Types of Undesirable Behaviours in the Classroom

Themes	Sub-themes	Tt1	Tt2	Tt3	Tt4	N
Violations of School Regulations	Lateness	✓	✓		✓	3
	Smoking	✓	✓			2
	Cheating	✓			✓	2
	Not attending regularly in the class		✓		✓	2
Doing something in private	Doing irrelevant activities in the class		✓			1
Violations of school work requirement	Hyperactivity and lack of concentration	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
	Not doing home work	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
	lack of interest in cultural activities and theatre play	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Transgressions against teacher and school administrators	Disobedience to carry out commands and instructions		✓		✓	2
	Rudeness with teacher / Talking back	✓	✓		✓	3
Violations of inter-personal relations (with other children)	Not having a health communication		✓			1
	Getting other children into trouble		✓		✓	2
Undesirable personality traits and morality	Being rude	✓	✓		✓	1
	Noisy speech		✓		✓	2
	Lying	✓	✓			2
	Lack of Personal hygiene				✓	1
	Selfishness			✓		1
	Silence	✓		✓		2
	Complaint about their teachers, friends	✓				1
	Swearing or profanity		✓			1
	Naughtiness			✓		1
Damaging and	Damaging school equipment				✓	1

stealing the property	Theft	✓	1
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Table 3 indicates the summary of Turkish teachers' views on types of students' undesirable behaviours inside classroom. The responses were classified into seven main themes and six of them further were divided into 22 sub-themes. The common reported classroom undesirable behaviour by all teachers was hyperactivity and lack of concentration and not doing homework. Next, being rude and late (75%), disobedience to carry out instruction and commands, not doing homework, presence in off-duty behaviour such as playing in the classroom, cheating, smoking, not attending in the class, getting other children into trouble, noisy speech, poor in personal hygiene were the frequently reported behaviours by two out of four (50%) teachers. Because of limitation of space, some teachers' opinions on the subject were cited below:

“Being late to school and changing it as habitual actions, not doing their homework, taking other students' work, and not giving important attention you need to make in class, telling lie, constantly producing a variety of excuse, complaint and disrespect, do not keep up with the rules of students such as not participate in the cultural activities and in the theatre play that allow student to strong socially and being silence, smoking cigarette secretly. In addition, students' failure to show the necessarily behaviours of the students when teacher is lecturing in the classroom are the common undesirable behaviours” (Tt1).

“Student undesirable behaviours I have often encountered are being late, talking without asking permission in the lesson, not doing homework, and there is a contract to read books in the school for 20 minutes per a day and their habit of reading books are usually weak- not obeying the contract. In addition, disturbing the regular lesson of a teacher, not attending in the classroom, being late, being lie, swearing speech, disobedience etc. are types of undesirable behaviours students in the classroom.”(Tt2).

“Being naughtiness, careful lacking, and selfish habitual habits are more common” (Tt3).

At the last as mentioned by teacher Tt4:

“Do not obey the rules of cleanliness, commands and etiquette, rude and abusive speech, not to be careful and attentive to the lesson. In addition, dealing with other affairs, not listening to lessons, prevent their friends from listening and working, behaving rude at

their friends and even their teacher, damaging their friends' property, being late to the school and being absent without reason, make a copy are the major undesirable behaviours showed in the classroom and in the school as a whole".

Further comparison about how difference between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views on types of undesirable behaviours was made. In terms of ranking of the top most frequently encountered undesirable behaviours by Ethiopian teachers were cheating and not doing the assigned tasks, however hyperactivity and lack of concentration were the problems encountered by Turkish teachers. The findings as presented in Table 2 and 3 also show there are unique problem not mentioned by other country teacher, for example, smoking by Turkish teachers, but not sitting properly and attaching nickname to their friends by Ethiopian teachers.

D. Teachers' views about the causes of undesirable behaviours in classroom

The views of Ethiopian and Turkish teachers about the causes of students' undesirable behaviours in the classroom were given in table 4 and 5 respectively. Finally, the **differences** between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views about causes of undesirable behaviours were added.

Table 4: Ethiopian Teachers' Views about the Causes of Undesirable Behaviour in Classroom

Causes	Et1	Et2	Et3	Et4	N
School-related	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Teacher-related	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Family-related	✓	✓		✓	3
Student-related	✓	✓			2
Environment-related			✓	✓	2
Physical conditions of the class-related	✓		✓		2
Lesson-related		✓	✓		2
Friends-related	✓				1

Table 4 illustrates that the all the observed frequencies showed that school and teachers are causes of classroom undesirable behaviour of the students. Then seventy-five percent of respondents are attributed the cause to family. However, the least only one teacher argued friends as a cause for undesirable behaviour. Let us see in-depth:

a. School related factors

The student may go to negative behaviours when he / she sees the effort of success is prevented because of lack of resources in the school. For example, as one teacher described:

“A number of variables such as the physical characteristics of the school, its status, the number of students, rules and management structure influence students’ attitudes and behaviours. The absence or inadequacy of the materials, tools and resources required for education and training is another cause of student undesirable behaviour” (Et4).

b. Teacher-related factors

Top among the most important teacher-related causes include teacher qualifications on the quality and success of classroom management (Et4), a particular teacher's instruction style (Et3), inadequacies of teachers (Et2). In addition if the teacher puts exaggerated and meaningless rules, if the teacher uses the note as a threat, students might show undesirable behaviours (Et1).

c. Family-related factors

The problems that affect student behaviours might arise from their family such as the number of individuals in the family, income and educational status of the family. For example, as one teacher’s described:

“When family over-supervised in child education, strict discipline or excessive disinterest, refusal and neglect, inconsistency in care and education, the students might show undesired behaviour in the classroom. Moreover, lack of bounds, lack of supervision, grown-up without any limits, heavy penalties, being orphanage” (ET1).

d. Student-related factors

The level of interaction of the students with the teacher and his / her friends is low, inadequate in social skills, the absence of good friend, not loving school, being in a state of dissatisfaction with society and the need to attract attention (Et1 & Et2).

e. Environment-related factors

Closeness and distances, the educational levels of the people living in environment are significantly influential on the behaviours of the students, so they moved to reflecting that behaviour into the classroom (Et3 & Et4).

f. Physical conditions of the class

The physical conditions of the class, *poor seating arrangements, a high noise level*, the noisy and crowded formation, number of students in the class might be affecting the behaviour of students (Et1 & Et3).

g. Lesson-related factors

A student who is bored from the lesson can show much undesirable behaviour. If the student's opinion is not taken in the school, class rules and class activities, if the teacher has power use, if the teacher puts exaggerated and meaningless rules, if the teacher uses the note as a threat; they might be bored from the lesson and show undesirable behaviour to coming against authority (Et1, Et3).

h. Friend-related factors

Friendship with children who have undesirable behaviour could lead to the development of undesirable behaviours of student (Et1).

Table 5: Turkish Teachers' views about the Causes of Undesirable Behaviour in Classroom

Causes	Tt1	Tt2	Tt3	Tt4	N
Family-related	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Teacher-related	✓	✓	✓	✓	4
Student-related	✓	✓		✓	3
Friends-related	✓	✓		✓	3
Environment-related		✓	✓	✓	3
Lesson-related				✓	1
School-related	✓				1

As can be seen in table 5, the intensity of each cause is almost different from the other cause; however, all teachers attributed the cause to family and teacher.

i. Family-related factors

All teachers attributed the major problems are starting from the family such as household substance condition, lack in support and follow-up, single grown-up in technique, lack of rules in the home. On the other hand, a teacher would give example directly:

".....If the family is not interesting to a child's learning level, not behaving appropriately with the child's development, the child may behave unwelcome because of things

connected with the physical needs of the child. Moreover, such child may remain asleep and do not have breakfast in the morning. In addition, the status of the family, household substance condition can be the reasons" (Tt2).

j. Teacher-related factors

From the teachers' side, the techniques that teacher use and ways of warm students' might cause undesirable behaviours in the classroom. One teacher said:

".....When they are lecturing - for example, if traditional, monotonic techniques are used, students are not careful and may exhibit undesirable behaviour. In addition, if the teacher does not benefit from technology and if the students are not interested, then they can affect their behaviour in a negative way" (Tt2).

k. Student-related factors

On the side of the student, as most teachers argued, there are things like inadequate feeling and perception for learning; low interest and desire for learning can be the reasons for the student's undesirable behaviour. Moreover, two teachers added

".....if the student does not express him / her and has a speech problem, he / she might behave unwelcome because of his illness. They may also behave unfavourably to students with the intention of attracting attention, interest and love" (Tt2).

And,

"...in the evening, students do not do homework while watching movies on TV, and when they go to school, they steal from other friends, which is undesirable"(Tt1).

l. Others

As far as the causes are concerned, qualifications of curricula and plans, qualifications of curricula and plans, the environment they live related to imitation and attention, friends' surroundings can cause undesirable behaviours as mentioned by participants.

Differences between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views about causes of undesirable behaviours

Figure 1: Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views about causes of undesirable behaviours

As can be seen in the above figure 1, further comparison between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views about causes of undesirable behaviours' was made. All as a common, attributed to teacher. However, differences were found between teachers' attributing student undesirable behaviours. In terms of ranking of the top most frequently attributed undesirable behaviours by Ethiopian teachers were school, teachers, and then families. However, all Turkish teachers attributed the cause to family and teacher and then student, friends and environment. From the side of Turkish teachers, no one has mentioned physical layout of the class as an attributed factors. Nevertheless, two Ethiopian teachers have mentioned it.

E. Teachers' techniques to cope up with the undesirable behaviours' in the classroom

Ethiopian and Turkish Teachers' techniques to cope up with the undesirable behaviours' in the classroom were given in table 6 and 7 respectively.

Table 6: Ethiopian Teachers' Techniques to Cope up with the Undesirable behaviours' in the Classroom

Strategies	Sub--Strategies	Et1	Et2	Et3	Et4	N
Punishment	Punishing			✓	✓	2
	Ignoring the behaviour			✓		1
	Warning with words			✓	✓	2
Reinforcement	Distracting student with positive behaviour or model	✓		✓		2
	Trust the students	✓				1

	Giving praise like books, smart words, medal	✓		✓	2	
	Giving more attention/care to student	✓	✓	✓	3	
Working with students	Playing games		✓		1	
	Having a direct discussion with student	✓			1	
	Developing a student contract /rules		✓	✓	2	
Working mutually with school stakeholders	Co-operating with school administrators	✓		✓	2	
	Contacting and working with family		✓	✓	2	
Keeping Busy	Giving more tasks	✓	✓		2	
Asking help from experts	Consulting with counsellor			✓	1	
Teaching Methodologies	Using different teaching methods		✓		1	
	Using more body language			✓	✓	2
	Changing tasks based on their interests			✓	1	

Table 6 summarizes that the categorization of four Ethiopian primary school teachers' responses based on techniques used to manage different types of students 'undesirable behaviours inside classroom. The responses classified into seven main themes and five of them further divided into 17 sub-themes. Teachers reported using a wide range of the 17 possible strategies. The common reported strategy used by 75% of respondents was giving more attention/care to student. Next, nearly half of respondents used more body language, give more tasks, contact and work with family at sever stage, develop a student contract /rules at the beginning, distract student with positive behaviour or model and punishing in proportion to the undesirable behaviour. Some Participants' opinions on the subject are cited below:

a. Punishment

Whatever teachers said sometimes in their speaking on their usage of punishment such as punishing, ignore the behaviour, warning, they are used and using it. For example,

".....Sometimes if i still cannot cope with the undesirable behaviour of the students even though I use other methods, the last reaction is punishment in proportion to the behaviour, to prevent the repetition of that behaviour, for those students who know why he or she punished"(Et4).

".....Rarely I punishing, ignoring, and warning students to stop bad behaviours' in the classroom" (Et3).

b. Reinforcement

Most teachers reported that when they faced undesirable behaviours' in the classroom, they focus on the positive action such as distract student with positive behaviour or model, catch students being good and trust, give praise like books, smart words, medal for good behaviours' (indirect reinforcement) and give more attention/care to student. E.g.:

"...First, I show concerned behaviours'. For example 'yes, I got you, I sense you or I understood you' are verbal statements indicate that i am concerned and careful about behaviours. In the process of reducing negative behaviours and improving positive behaviours in the pupils, I as a teacher often use positive expressions against my students to distract them positively, pay attention to my clothes and physical appearance to become a model"(Et3).

In addition, Et1 added:

" It is necessary to take care of the child. If the child wants to be self-confident and have a good behaviour, then the parent or teacher must trust the child first. In addition to trusting and encourage my students, I tried to become a model for behaviours that students want to see".

c. Working with students

It is necessary to take care of the child. Teachers reported that to cope up with students undesirable behaviours' in the classroom, they playing games, have a direct discussion with student to know the causes, develop a student contract /rules at the beginning.

"...the method I used mostly by having discussion with students who show undesirable behaviours in the classroom. The time to spend together is not quantity but quality also important" (Et1).

d. Working mutually with school stakeholders

Most teachers emphasized that to deal and solve the undesirable behaviours of students show in the classroom, mutual work of all stakeholders is important.

"When I am unable to cope with behaviours that create distress within the classroom and obstruct education, I may ask the family or school management for help in solving the problem of the students" (Et4).

e. Keeping busy

Give more tasks or homework to the students is also identified by teachers. For example,

".... I also giving a task to occupy students or changing their work to another task that is more interesting to them, which is a useful way to prevent from boring on lesson or tasks" (Et4).

f. Asking help from experts

One teacher emphasized that to deal and solve the undesirable behaviours of students show in the classroom, getting help from counsellor is important.

"When I am unable to cope with behaviours that create distress within the classroom and obstruct education, I may ask an expert for help in solving the problem of the students" (Et4).

g. Teaching methodologies

On the side of teaching learning process, changing tasks such as home works based on their interests, use more body language se different teaching methods are techniques' used by teacher to cope up the undesirable behaviours' in the classroom. For example:

"..... In order to prevent students from showing any undesirable behaviour because boring from the lessons, I should be used sound tone mimics well, develop all attractive methods that should be dominated by all classes. At that time, I can make students more active and take their attention" (Et2).

"In the face of undesirable student behaviours, understands the problem and then I can awake up a student by using the body language such as touching and asking students directly" (Et4).

Table 7: Turkish Teachers' Techniques to Cope up with the Undesirable Behaviours in the Classroom

Strategies	Sub--Strategies	Tt1	Tt2	Tt3	Tt4	N
Simple Punishment	Warning with words	✓				1
Reinforcement	Distracting student with positive behaviour or model	✓		✓	✓	3
	Trust students			✓		1
	Giving praise like books, smart words, medal	✓		✓	✓	3

	Giving more attention/care to student	✓	1
Working with students	Playing games	✓	1
	Having a direct discussion with student	✓	1
Working mutually with school stakeholders	Co-operating with the school administrators	✓	1
	Contacting and working with family	✓	1
Asking help from experts	Consulting with counsellor	✓ ✓	2
Teaching methodologies	Using different teaching methods	✓	1
	Changing tasks based on their interests	✓	1
	Making students to learn by doing, living and sharing	✓	1
	Asking questions and writing notes	✓	1

Table 7 shows that responses of four Turkish primary school teachers' techniques used to manage different types of students' undesirable behaviours in the classroom. The responses classified into six main themes and five of them further divided into 15 sub-themes. Teachers reported using a wide range of the 15 possible strategies. The common reported strategy used by 75% of respondents was positive reinforcement, which is providing of praise like books, smart words, medal for good behaviour. Next, consult with school counselor:

a. Punishment

Only one Turkish teacher said:

"....Firstly, warn students who do not comply with the rules. In some cases, i use simple penalties for fearful purposes" (Tt1).

b. Reinforcement

Most teachers reported that when they faced undesirable behaviours' in the classroom, they focus on the positive action such as distract student with positive behaviour or model, catch students being good and trust, give praise like books, smart words, medal for good behaviours (indirect reinforcement) and give more attention/care to student. For example:

"....Positive awards are important - for example, a student who reads many books and do a lot of homework can be awarded in a beautiful shape like well done, one Turkish lira, a cheap item, a chocolate certificate and the medal" (Tt1).

In addition, one teacher added by saying

"To stop undesirable behaviour, for example, a student who misbehaviour in classroom, I can eliminate by praising his or her friend's class for careful listening, instead of reacting directly" (Tt4).

c. Working with students

Teachers reported that to cope up with students undesirable behaviours' in the classroom, they playing games, have a direct discussion with student to know the causes.

"....First, I need to get to know student better in every aspects. Not only the physical dimension of students, but also every aspects-family situation and especially in which environment live, how transportation affects , families' environment and what troubles can a child encounter after going to school" (Tt2).

d. Working mutually with school stakeholders

Like Ethiopian teachers, Turkish teachers emphasized that to deal and solve the undesirable behaviours' students show in the classroom, mutual work of all stakeholders is important. E.g.

".....Speak out first with student and then i will call his or her family." (Tt1).

e. Asking help from experts

If the problem not become under control after interviewed with his or her family, i contact with the experts on the issue to handle it.

".....After the family interviewed but if shel/he is not change on that undesirable behaviour, he/she would be sent to the school counsellor to identity the problem." (Tt1).

f. Teaching methodologies

On the side of teaching learning process, changing tasks such as home works based on their interests, asking questions and writing note, make students to learn by doing, living and sharing, use different teaching methods were techniques used by teacher to cope up the undesirable behaviours in the classroom. For example:

".....For example, in classroom, when you teach one character- let us say -ş , students can learn it more quickly in the form of games such as call friend by saying -ş (with

sound) look at me (bak bana), ş-come on now (ş-şimdi gel), ş sing songs (ş-şarkıları söyle)” (Tt3).

“.....When I know the causes and what I need to do, I use separate management techniques depending on the situation and scientific interview” (Tt2).

Moreover, Tt4 added:

“.....Sometimes, I have written a note to student about what is the behaviour of the student’s behaviour, in addition, i tell the student’s name and ask the question directly to take the attention of the student”.

Further comparison about what are the differences between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers’ techniques to cope up with the undesirable behaviour was made. All as a common, they focus more or less on the positive action such as distract student with positive behaviour or model, indirect reinforcement) and use of different teaching methodologies. However, differences were found between Ethiopian and Turkish teachers. In terms of ranking of the top most frequently, techniques for Turkish teachers were positive reinforcement, which is providing of praise, but for Ethiopian teachers giving more attention/care to student. Even if both teachers applied reinforcement. From the side of Turkish teachers, no one has mentioned about making a student contract /rules at the beginning, give more tasks and more body language as techniques. Nevertheless, most Ethiopians have mentioned it. In addition, more number of Ethiopian teachers has used more punishment than Turkish.

F. Teachers’ Suggestions for other teachers regarding ways of managing the undesirable behaviours of the primary school students in the classroom

At the end of the interview, teachers were asked to suggest based on their experiences for other teachers to cope with the undesirable behaviours of students in the classroom.

Here, their responses were shortly presented below:

“Create “can-do” attitude on the mind of students and co-operation”. (Et1)

“Creates a democratic environment, not use the wrong reinforcement in the teaching class”. (Et2)

“Know the environment, economic, social, cultural background and resources of students very well, make appropriate lesson time (not more than 50 minutes) and use diversify instructional strategy”. (Et3)

“Observe the entire class with his / her eyes during the class and given students the opportunity to be active, discover the level of interest of the students with a good observation, discuss the current situation if the signs of disturbance and boredoms are seen, use logic and intelligence games, and allow free activity for a few minutes, and so on. The teacher also must make statements about the behaviours that he / she expects from the students at first class”. (Et4)

“First talking with the student. If it is not enough, it is necessary to interview the family and if it is not enough again, the guidance of therapist can investigate and resolve causes, and might be using drugs.” (Tt1)

“Knowing better-the teacher needs to know more about student development, use different technological tools that attract attention of the students, interviewing with the pupil family, visiting home, asking for help from specialists and guidance teachers”. (Tt2)

“Guided students in behaviour rather than in information race and with pictures, music, drama lessons or workshops and with their teachers”. (Tt3)

“Expressing the right behaviour and positive result”. (Tt4)

4. Discussion

The present study attempted to examine classroom undesirable behaviours as perceived by primary school teachers. The Ethiopian teachers mentioned eight main themes with 21 sub-themes of undesirable behaviours. However, Turkish teachers' responses classified into seven main themes and six of them further divided into 22 sub-themes with hyperactivity and lack of concentration as common. Even if the way of categorization of present findings different from other Authors' classification, the internal sub-themes showed similar to those studies conducted in the Singapore, Ethiopia, and Turkey contexts. As Ethiopian teachers reported, the common reported classroom undesirable behaviours were cheating and not doing the assigned tasks such as homework, personal hygiene, being rude and late. This finding consistent with a study conducted in Guji Zone in Ethiopia (Getiye, T., 2015, p.39), which were ranked as

follow: cheating on tests and in-class assignments, being lateness or misses to class, even if failing to bring necessary materials to class and violating the school dress code were not mentioned in the study. The study also nearly similar with Alemayehu (2012, p.43-44) study on Shamashemene secondary school students in Ethiopia, but the complaints on the use cell phone was not listed in the study. In addition, the types of the undesirable behaviours that the researchers found were in the line with a study in Singapore (Tan, E. & Yuanshan, C. (1999, p.3), Amogne (2014, s.23) in Ethiopia. Even if Lewis (1991) has distinguished three overlapping types of undesirable, namely: undesirable that inhibits the learner's own learning, undesirable by one learner, which is destructive to the learning of another, and undesirable, which is disrespectful, defiant or abusive to the educator, the sub-themes were nearly similar with the present finding. Moreover, the study has a consistence with the study in Turkey (Balay, R and Sağlam, M., 2008, & Çetin, B., 2015).

Because different kinds of undesirable behaviour and each one has, different causes which has negative impact on classroom management (Dhaliwal, 2013). Table 4 illustrates that the all the observed frequencies of Ethiopian teachers showed that school and teachers are causes of classroom undesirable behaviour of the students. Next, teachers attributed the cause to family. However, all Turkish teachers attributed the cause to family and teacher (table5). The first finding (as Ethiopian reported) is inconsistent with the study of Tan and Yuanshan (1999, p.8), which showed teachers identify possible causes for the behavioural problems encountered to unconducive home environment, negative peer pressure, and poor parenting as the most frequently cited reason and the next to be blamed are adverse influences of the media promoting materialistic values. But, whatever the frequencies, the factors as a whole has consistence. It has also a bit different with the finding of Alemayehu, (2012, p.52) and Getiye, (2015, p.45) in Ethiopia, which reported top among the most important causes include student-related factors (which was not common but reported by some teachers). The study also go in line with the findings of Amogne (2014, p.25) showed that peer group influence, family background, school environment, considering the act as adventure and lack of vision (long term aim) by students were identified as the dominant factors contributing to undesirable behaviours among students.

The present finding also indicated that to cope up with the undesirable behaviours of students, teachers used different teaching methodologies, taking advice or suggestions from an expert, mutual work with school stakeholders (collaborative strategies), work with students, positive action or reinforcement, simple punishment. This finding consistent with the finding of Getiye, (2015, p.47) in Ethiopia, results were the use collaborative strategies and strengthening school and community relationship.

In addition the present study also in line with studies in Turkey as Çetin (2015), Yilmaz, (2008) and Başar (2001) presented teachers' solutions to undesirable behaviours were punishments and awards, behaving more sincerely towards students, guidance service, giving assignment, making students sit in front of the class, and playing games.

5. Conclusion, Implication and Recommendations

The overall aim of this study was to identify Ethiopian and Turkish teachers' views about types and causes of students' undesirable behaviours and the techniques they use to cope up. Further comparisons about what are the differences between Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' views on the issues were made.

Researchers found from the study that students' undesirable behaviours were a big challenge in teaching-learning and teachers have reported the presence of almost all kinds of students' undesirable behaviour irrespective of the differences in the nature, and background of the schools. As Ethiopian teacher reported, the common reported classroom undesirable behaviours were cheating and not doing the assigned tasks such as homework, personal hygiene, being rude and late. However, Turkish teachers reported hyperactivity and lack of concentration, being rude and late. Regarding the causes of undesirable behaviours of the students, the intensity of each cause is almost different from the other cause; however, all teachers attributed the cause to teacher (which is in-class factor). As Oliveira, & Amândio, 2013, p.9, suggested a teacher who believes that a student's undesirable is caused by problems at home may feel no "ownership" of the problem and therefore be less likely to explore teacher-focused intervention strategies, like the use of different teaching styles or a critical examination of their class environment. However, the participants' thoughts were well since they attributed to themselves. In addition, generally, they attributed to both out-of- class and in-class factors. Teachers tend to attribute the cause for undesirable behaviour of the students in the school, more internal factors than to external ones. Moreover, Turkish and Ethiopian teachers' techniques that they use to cope up with the undesirable behaviour have been examined. Teachers used a wide variety of strategies, with all the strategies being used at least sometimes. All as a common, they focus more or less on the positive action such as distract student with positive behaviour or model, indirect reinforcement) and use of different teaching methodologies. However, differences were found between Ethiopian and Turkish teachers. In terms of ranking of the top most frequently, techniques for Turkish teachers were positive reinforcement, which is providing of praise, but for Ethiopian teachers giving more attention/care to student. Finally, teachers have suggested for other teachers about the techniques to cope up with

the undesirable behaviour. Because of social and cultural influences, there are difference views on types and causes of undesirable behaviours of students and techniques to cope up.

Based on the findings, the researchers have made the following recommendations and practical implications:

- The researchers also believed all suggestions recommended by teachers should be considered and have been given credibility.
- The teachers should be realizing self-esteem of the pupils, which are constructive approaches to preventing undesirable behaviours.
- To tackle the undesirable behaviours, the teachers should advocate and have home visits to forge a strong home-school partnership and not use punishment, which cause some adverse effects.
- Supervisors, principals, assistance principals and teachers should be committed to cope up with the undesirable behaviours of students in a professional manner.
- A study needs to be carried out on the side of students by asking them directly to see whether findings from the study will encounter with the ones from this research. In addition, with greater involvement of all stakeholders of the school there is a need to conduct an action-research for scanning the internal and external environment pertaining to undesirable behaviours of students.

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